

A New Synthesis of 7-Ethyl-8-methyl-1,2-benzofluorene: Jacobs Hydrocarbon

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A new synthesis of 7-ethyl-8-methyl-1,2-benzofluorene (Jacobs hydrocarbon) is described from 2,1-methoxycarbonyl-ethyl-4,5-benzindan-1-one (IV: R = Me), which has been prepared by two independent routes. The keto-ester (IV: R = Me) on the Stobbe condensation, followed by decarboxylation and esterification, affords the unsaturated di-ester (VIII). The saturated ester (IX: R = Me) or the corresponding acid on cyclisation provides a tetracyclic ketone (X), which on Grignard reaction, followed by dehydration and dehydrogenation, furnishes the desired hydrocarbon (I) in an excellent yield.

Through selenium dehydrogenation of jervine¹ and veratramine², Jacobs *et al.* first isolated a hydrocarbon, m.p. 153.5-55.5°. The same compound was also obtained from the dehydrogenation of other natural products³, such as drevogenin^{3a}, condurangogenins^{3b}, and sarcostein^{3c}. The first synthesis of this important dehydrogenation product by Reichstein *et al.*⁴, definitely established the structure of this hydrocarbon, and thus the skeletal structure of many complex compounds. A straight forward synthesis of the above hydrocarbon is described in the present communication.

The Dieckmann cyclisation of ethyl β -(2-ethoxycarbonyl-1-naphthyl) propionate (II)⁵ with sodium dust under benzene, followed by alkylation *in situ* with ethyl bromoacetate, provided the desired alkylated product (III: R = H)⁵ in a reasonably good yield. In the present case, when ethyl α -bromopropionate was used as the alkylating agent, the above procedure yielded only the unchanged β -keto-ester. When potassium dust was substituted for sodium, the alkylation with ethyl α -bromopropionate afforded at least some amount of the desired product (III: R = Me). This observation finds support from the fact⁶ that in aprotic solvent of low dielectric constant, the nature of the cation plays an important role on the nucleophilicity of the anion (here the carbanion). The above alkylation in a mixture of benzene and dimethylformamide increased the yield of the desired product (III: R = Me) to about 85%. This favourable effect of dimethylformamide on solubility and reactivity of carbanions in alkylation reactions is well known^{6,7}. The acidic hydrolysis of the product (III: R = Me) afforded crystalline 2,1'-carboxyethyl-4,5-benzindan-1-one (IV: R = H) and a neutral material characterised as 4,5-benzindan-1-one (V)⁵ in 79 and 12% yield respectively. Isolation of the ketone (V) from the above hydrolysis indicates that the main product (III: R = Me) is contaminated with some of its isomeric

1. Jacobs *et al.*, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1941, 141, 51.
2. Jacobs and Sato, *ibid.*, 1949, 181, 55.
3. (a) Winkler and Reichstein, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1954, 37, 721; (b) Korte, *Chem. Ber.*, 1955, 88, 1527; Korte and Weitkamp, *ibid.*, 1956, 89, 2669; (c) Nascimento *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1959, 42, 661; (d) Cornforth, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1959, 602; (e) Mitsuhashi and Shimizu, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1962, No. 20, 909, *et seq.*
4. Keller *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1958, 41, 1633.
5. Bardhan *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 355.
6. Kornblum *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 85, 1148.
7. Zaugg *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1960, 82, 2895, 2903; 1961, 83, 837; *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, 26, 644; Marshall and Cannon, *ibid.*, 1956, 21, 245; Stork and Burgstahler, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 3544.

O-alkylated product, which is not unusual⁸. The structure of the keto-acid (IV: R=H) was established by its unambiguous synthesis from 4,5-benzindan-1-one⁹ (V). This ketone on careful bromination in chloroform afforded the desired bromoketone (VI: R=H) in an excellent yield; excess bromine yielded a dibromo compound which was most probably 2,2-dibromo-4,5-benzindan-1-one (VI: R=Br). The bromoketone (VI: R=H) was condensed with ethyl sodiomalonate to furnish diethyl 1-oxo-4,5-benzindan-2-yl-malonate (VII: R=H) which on methylation afforded crystalline diethyl 1-oxo-4,5-benzindan-2-yl-methyl-malonate (VII: R=Me) in practically quantitative yield. The above methylated product on acid or alkaline hydrolysis, followed by decarboxylation, yielded the same keto-acid (IV: R=H), reported above. This keto-acid failed to provide a ketonic derivative under usual conditions and showed IR absorption at 1730 and 1667 cm^{-1} , comparable to that of 1-keto-2-indunylacetic acid, reported by House *et al*⁹.

2,1'-Methoxycarbonyl-ethyl-4,5-benzindan-1-one (IV: R=Me), prepared from the above keto-acid, on the Stobbe condensation¹⁰, followed by acid treatment and esterification, furnished methyl β -(2,1'-methoxycarbonyl-ethyl-6,7-benz-3-indenyl)propionate (VIII) in 60% yield, based on the keto-ester (IV: R=Me) employed. The UV absorption of (VIII) at 262 μ suggests presence of the styrene system and the endo double bond is preferred due to the fact that where an exocyclic double bond might be expected in the indane series, the endocyclic form is often encountered, even at the expense of conjugation with C=O of an ethoxycarbonyl group¹¹. Catalytic reduction of (VIII) afforded methyl β -(2,1'-methoxycarbonyl-ethyl-4,5-benz-1-indanyl)propionate (IX: R=Me) in nearly 90% yield. The acid or alkaline hydrolysis of (IX: R=Me) furnished a crystalline dicarboxylic acid (IX: R=H) in good yield. The lead salt of this acid on pyrolysis afforded a stereoisomeric mixture of ketones (X), m.p. 80-120° in 50% yield. The Dieckmann cyclisa-

8. Kurosawa and Fujisi, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1963, 1688.

9. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, 27, 4141.

10. Johnson *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 514.

11. Ahmed and Campbell, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 4115; Bone and Cort, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1961, 22.

tion of the ester (IX : R=Me) in presence of potassium *t*-butoxide¹², followed by acid hydrolysis and decarboxylation, provided the same ketonic material, m.p. 80-120°, in 70% yield. It may be mentioned that a single attempt to effect cyclisation of the ester (IX : R=Me) with sodium hydride was unsuccessful. From the above mixture of ketones, a pure ketone, m.p. 142°, was isolated. The ketone mixture, m.p. 80-120°, afforded two isomeric 2,4-DNP derivatives: A, m.p. 230°, and B, m.p. 257-58°. The derivative B was also prepared in good yield from the pure ketone, m.p. 142°. The equilibration of the pure ketone, m.p. 142°, with sodium methoxide, according to the procedure of Sorkin *et al.*¹³, furnished the same mixture of ketones, m.p. 80-120°, which produced two isomeric 2,4-DNP derivatives, A and B, reported above.

The crystalline acid (IX : R = H), which was obtained through catalytic hydrogenation of (VIII), most probably has a *cis* configuration¹⁴, as depicted in (IX). Since cyclisation of the above crystalline acid or the corresponding ester afforded an isomeric mixture of ketones, it is evidently due to the epimeric centre (C₁₀ in X) adjacent to the carbonyl group.

The ketone mixture, m.p. 80-120°, on the Grignard reaction with ethylmagnesium iodide, followed by dehydration and dehydrogenation (Pd—C), afforded a hydrocarbon, m.p. 147-50° (51% based on the ketone used), which on purification by chromatography furnished pure 7-ethyl-8-methyl-1,2-benzofluorene (I). The mixed melting point of the above hydrocarbon with an authentic sample* of Jacobs hydrocarbon was undepressed. The spectral properties are also identical with those reported by Reichstein and his associates⁴.

The above method is a general one for the synthesis of all derivatives of 1, 2-benzofluorene, reported by Reichstein and his collaborators^{4, 15}.

12. Johnson *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 6331.

13. Sorkin and Reichstein, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1946, **29**, 1209.

14. Linstead *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **64**, 1985; Herz, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1955, **20**, 1062.

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• EXPERIMENTAL

2-Bromo-4,5-benzindan-1-one (VI: R = H).—To a solution of 4,5-benzindan-1-one¹ (1 g.) in dry chloroform (25 ml), cooled to 20°, was added dropwise with stirring a solution of bromine (960 mg.) in dry chloroform (12 ml), each drop of the bromine solution being added after decolorisation of the previous one. After complete addition of bromine, the reaction mixture was stirred at the room temperature (30°) for 1 hr. The chloroform solution was washed successively with water, sodium bicarbonate solution, and water, dried (CaCl₂), and the solvent removed to furnish the crystalline bromo compound (1.2 g.), m.p. 127-29°; recrystallisation from methanol yielded the pure material as colorless cubes, m.p. 132°. (Found: C, 60.06; H, 3.63; Br, 30.82. C₁₃H₉OBr requires C, 59.77; H, 3.44; Br, 30.66%). When the above bromination was carried out in ether solution and cooled in ice-salt bath, the unchanged ketone (V) was only isolated.

2,2-Dibromo-4,5-benzindan-1-one (VI: R = Br).—When the bromination of 4,5-benzindan-1-one (1 g.) in chloroform solution was performed as above, using a little more than two moles of bromine per mole of the ketone, a crystalline bromoketone (1.2 g.), m.p. 145-50°, was isolated. This material on three recrystallisations from methanol furnished colorless needles, m.p. 155-56°. (Found: C, 45.93; H, 2.81; Br, 47.40. C₁₃H₉OBr₂ requires C, 45.88; H, 2.35; Br, 47.06%). This bromoketone on keeping developed a red colour.

Diethyl 1-Oxo-4,5-benzindan-2-yl-maloxate (VII: R = H).—To a suspension of sodiomalonic ester, prepared from sodium dust (330 mg.), diethyl malonate (4.2 ml), and dry benzene (55 ml), was added dropwise with stirring a solution of 2-bromo-4,5-benzindan-1-one (3.5 g.) in dimethylformamide (20 ml). After stirring for 3 hr. at the room temperature, the reaction mixture was refluxed for 17 hr. This was then diluted with cold water, organic layer separated, and aqueous layer extracted with ether. The mixed organic solvent was washed with water, dried (Na₂SO₄), and evaporated. The residue on distillation afforded a colorless liquid (3.75 g.), b.p. 210-15°/0.4 mm. A middle cut was analysed. (Found: C, 70.85; H, 6.30. C₂₀H₂₀O₃ requires C, 70.57; H, 5.92%). The analytical sample on keeping solidified, m.p. 70-79°; three recrystallisations from ether-petroleum (b.p. 40-60°) afforded crystals, m.p. 85-86°. (Found: C, 70.29; H, 6.00%).

Diethyl 1-Oxo-4,5-benzindan-2-yl-methylmaloxate (VII: R = Me).—To a suspension of sodium dust (400 mg.) in dry benzene (30 ml) was added a solution of the above ester (VII: R = H; 3 g.) in dry benzene (20 ml) and the reaction mixture was left at the room temperature for 16 hr. To the dirty white sodium salt, thus obtained, methyl iodide (10 ml) was added and the reaction mixture refluxed for 11 hr. It was then diluted with ice-water, organic layer separated, and the aqueous layer extracted with ether. The combined solvent was washed with water, dried (Na₂SO₄), and evaporated. The solid residue (3 g.), m.p. 122-25°, thus obtained, on three recrystallisations from ether-light petroleum afforded the pure material, m.p. 133-34°. (Found: C, 71.44; H, 6.52. C₂₁H₂₂O₃ requires C, 71.17; H, 6.26%).

Ethyl α-(1-Oxo-2-ethoxycarbonyl-4,5-benz-2-indanyl)acetate (III: R = Me).—(a). To a suspension of potassium dust (1.8 g.) in dry benzene (100 ml) was added a solution

15. Osowiecki *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1958, 41, 1606.

*All m.p.s are uncorrected. The UV spectrum was measured by the Unicam spectrophotometer SP. 500.

of ethyl β -(2-ethoxycarbonyl-1-naphthyl)propionate⁵ (12 g.) in dry benzene (40 ml) and magnesium-dried ethanol (2 drops). The mixture was then refluxed under nitrogen for 2 hr. The cooled reaction mixture was treated with ethyl α -bromopropionate (16 ml) and dimethylformamide (50 ml), when all the potassium salt went into solution. After stirring (room temp., N_2 atmosphere) for 5 hr., the viscous mixture was refluxed for 6 hr. The cooled reaction mixture was diluted with water, organic layer separated, and the aqueous layer extracted with ether. The combined organic layer was washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4), and evaporated. The residue on distillation furnished a light yellow viscous oil (12.1 g.), b. p. 200-15°/0.4 mm; a middle fraction was collected for analysis. (Found: C, 70.64; H, 6.34. $C_{21}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 71.17; H, 6.26%.)

(b). When dimethylformamide was omitted in the above experiment, ethyl β -(2-ethoxycarbonyl-1-naphthyl)propionate⁵ (3 g.) provided a highly viscous alkylated product (1.6 g.), b. p. 190-210°/0.4 mm.

(c). The sodio-salt of the β -keto-ester, prepared from ethyl β -(2-ethoxycarbonyl-1-naphthyl)propionate (3 g.), was treated with ethyl α -bromopropionate (2 ml), following the procedure of Bardhan *et al*⁵. The reaction mixture was left at the room temperature for 16 hr. and then refluxed for 7 hr. The reaction mixture, obtained as cake, was treated with water and extracted with ether. The solid (1.5 g.), insoluble in ether and water, on acid hydrolysis afforded a ketonic material (850 mg.), m. p. 107-17°; this on two recrystallisations from ether-light petroleum furnished pure 4,5-benzindan-1-one⁵, m. p. 120-21°. The above ether solution on evaporation yielded an oil (0.8 g.) which was not characterised.

2,1'-Carboxyethyl-4,5-benzindan-1-one (IV: R=H).—(a). The preceding substituted β -keto-ester (III: R = Me; 21 g.) was refluxed with acetic acid (120 ml) and HCl (60 ml) for 12 hr. The acids were removed under water pump, the residue dissolved in ether, and the ethereal solution was washed with water and extracted with 2% KOH solution. The alkaline extract on acidification yielded a solid material (12 g.), which was probably a mixture of diastereoisomeric acids. This material on repeated recrystallisation from methanol afforded a pure isomer (7 g.), m.p. 185-86°. (Found: C, 75.32; H, 5.60. $C_{16}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 75.57; H, 5.55). λ_{max}^{EtOH} 251, 273, and 282 μ ($\log \epsilon$, 4.72, 3.90, and 3.97 respectively); IR absorption* at 1730 and 1667 cm^{-1} . This keto-acid failed to provide a semicarbazone under usual conditions. The neutral ether on evaporation furnished a solid residue which on sublimation at 150°/0.4 mm afforded 4,5-benzindan-1-one⁵ (1.5 g.), m.p. 112-13°. This material on two recrystallisations from methanol furnished the pure ketone, m. p. 120°; mixed m. p. with an authentic sample⁵ was undepressed.

(b). The substituted malonic ester (VII: R = Me; 1 g.) was heated under reflux with acetic acid (20 ml) and HCl (10 ml) for 9 hr. After working up as before, the crude keto-acid (750 mg.) was isolated. This material on crystallisations from methanol furnished the pure acid (410 mg.), m.p. 184-85°; mixed m.p. with the keto-acid, reported above, remained undepressed.

(c). The malonic ester (VII: R = Me; 1.3 g.) on the usual alkaline hydrolysis provided a malonic acid (1.25 g.), m.p. 183° (with decarboxylation), which on decarboxylation at 180-90° afforded the keto-acid (400 mg.), m.p. 179.81°.

*Determined as a suspension in a potassium bromide pellet.

2,1'-Methoxycarbonylethyl-4,5-benzindan-1-one (IV: R=Me).—The above keto-acid (crude, 12 g.) was esterified by refluxing with absolute methanol (150 ml) and H_2SO_4 (conc., 15 ml) for 16-18 hr. After usual working up, the ester was obtained as a pale yellow oil (11.9 g.), b.p. 190-95°/0.6 mm. A middle cut was analysed. (Found: C, 75.78; H, 5.66. $C_{17}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 76.10; H, 6.01%). λ_{max}^{EtOH} 251, 273, 282, 293, and 341 $m\mu$ (log ϵ , 4.66, 3.88, 3.96, 3.46, and 3.17 respectively).

The semicarbazone, m.p. 213-14°, separating from methanol on recrystallisation from the same solvent yielded crystals, m.p. 217-18° (decomp.). (Found: C, 66.20; H, 5.96; N, 12.87. $C_{16}H_{15}O_3N_3$ requires C, 66.44; H, 5.89; N, 12.92%).

Methyl β -(2,1'-Methoxycarbonylethyl-6,7-benz-3-indenyl)propionate (VIII).—To a stirred solution of potassium metal (4 g.) in dry *t*-butanol (83 ml) was added dropwise (room temp., N_2 atmosphere) a solution of 2,1'-methoxycarbonylethyl-4,5-benzindan-1-one (11.9 g.) and dimethyl succinate (22.5 g.) in *t*-butanol (25 ml). The deep brown reaction mixture was refluxed for 1 hr. and allowed to stand at the room temperature for 16 hr. The mixture was then acidified with HCl (dil.) and most of the alcohol was distilled at a reduced pressure. The residue was taken up in ether and the ethereal solution was washed with water and extracted with a 2% KOH solution. The alkaline solution was acidified and the liberated acid was extracted with ether. The extract was washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4), and evaporated to provide the crude half-ester (17 g.) as a semisolid mass. The neutral ether solution afforded mostly unchanged dimethyl succinate. The crude half-ester (17 g.), obtained above, was decarboxylated by refluxing for 12 hr. with a mixture of acetic acid (240 ml), hydrobromic acid (48%, 160 ml), and water (40 ml). The acids were removed under reduced pressure and the residue was extracted with ether. The ether was washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4), and evaporated to yield an acidic material (13 g.), which on esterification with dry methanol (200 ml) and H_2SO_4 (conc., 20 ml) furnished methyl β -(2,1'-methoxycarbonylethyl-6,7-benz-3-indenyl)propionate (8 g.) as a yellow viscous oil, b.p. 210-15°/0.4 mm. (Found: C, 74.08; H, 6.75. $C_{21}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 74.53; H, 6.55%). λ_{max}^{EtOH} 252, 262, 285, and 295 $m\mu$ (log ϵ , 4.61, 4.58, 3.69, and 3.72 respectively). The above unsaturated ester on alkaline hydrolysis did not furnish any crystalline acid.

Methyl β -(2,1'-Methoxycarbonylethyl-4,5-benz-1-indanyl) propionate (IX: R=Me).—The above unsaturated ester (8.4 g.) was hydrogenated with 10% Pd-C (350 mg.) in ethanol (40 ml). The theoretical amount of hydrogen was absorbed within 4 hr. The product on vacuum distillation afforded the reduced ester (7.9 g.) as a pale yellow viscous oil, b.p. 195-200°/0.4 mm. (Found: C, 73.72; H, 7.08. $C_{21}H_{24}O_4$ requires C, 74.09; H, 7.11%). λ_{max}^{EtOH} 251, 275, 280, and 291 $m\mu$ (log ϵ , 3.77, 3.62, 3.65, and 3.55 respectively).

β -(2,1'-Carboxyethyl-4,5-benz-1-indanyl) propionic Acid (IX: R=H).—(a) The above reduced ester (4.1 g.) was refluxed for 9 hr. with a solution of KOH (4.1 g.) in methanol (25 ml). The aqueous alkaline solution after treatment with ether was acidified to provide a solid acid (3.7 g.), m.p. 212-16°, which on recrystallisation from dilute methanol furnished the pure dicarboxylic acid, m.p. 222°. (Found: C, 73.16; H, 6.53. $C_{19}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 73.06; H, 6.45%).

(b) The reduced ester (2 g.) on refluxing for 12 hr. with a mixture of acetic acid (10 ml), HCl (conc., 8 ml), and water (3 ml) yielded the above dicarboxylic acid (1.8 g.), which on crystallisation from methanol furnished the pure acid, m.p. 222°.

10-*Methyl-6b*, 7, 8, 9, 10, 10a-*hexahydro-9-ozochrysofluorene* (X).—(a). The lead salt, prepared from β -(2,1'-carboxyethyl-4,5-benz-1-indanyl)propionic acid (2.2 g.) and lead carbonate (6 g.), on pyrolysis at 250-320° afforded a solid ketone (900 mg.), m.p. 80-120°. This material on repeated (5 times) recrystallisation from methanol afforded a pure isomer, m.p. 142°. (Found: C, 86.63; H, 7.27. $C_{18}H_{18}O$ requires C, 86.36; H, 7.25%). This ketone (50 mg.), m.p. 142°, furnished a DNP (50 mg.), m.p. 251-52°, which on recrystallisation from chloroform-ethyl acetate afforded an orange material, m.p. 257-58° (decomp.). (Found: C, 66.82; H, 5.31; N, 12.57. $C_{24}H_{22}O_4N_4$ requires C, 66.96; H, 5.15; N, 13.02%).

The DNP (350 mg.), obtained from the ketone (250 mg., m.p. 80-120°), on treatment with benzene furnished an insoluble fraction, m.p. 254°, which on recrystallisation from chloroform-ethyl acetate yielded an orange material (100 mg.), m.p. 257-58°, identical with the DNP, reported above. The benzene solution was chromatographed on alumina and the benzene eluate on evaporation furnished yellow-orange crystals (200 mg.), m.p. 225-27°, which on three recrystallisations from chloroform-ethyl acetate afforded crystals, m.p. 230° (decomp.). (Found: C, 66.66; H, 5.09; N, 12.79. $C_{24}H_{22}O_4N_4$ requires C, 66.96; H, 5.15; N, 13.02%).

(b). Potassium (2.9 g.) was dissolved in *t*-butanol (70 ml) and the excess alcohol was removed by distillation. The last trace of the alcohol was removed by repeated distillation with dry benzene. To the suspension of potassium *t*-butoxide¹², thus prepared, in dry benzene (75 ml) was added slowly (N_2 atmosphere, room temp.) with stirring a solution of methyl β -(2,1'-methoxycarbonyl-ethyl-4,5-benz-1-indanyl)propionate (3.5 g.) in dry benzene (75 ml). The resulting red solution was stirred for 1 hr. and then refluxed for 4 hr. After keeping at the room temperature for 16 hr., the greenish black mass was decomposed by H_2SO_4 (ice-cold). The organic layer separated and the aqueous portion was extracted with ether. The combined solvent was washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4), and evaporated to provide a solid product (3.25 g.) which showed a greenish violet ferric reaction. The β -keto-ester, thus obtained, was hydrolysed and decarboxylated by refluxing for 2½ hr. with a mixture of acetic acid (70 ml), HCl (conc., 35 ml), and water (12 ml). The acids were removed under vacuum and the residue was dissolved in ether. The ethereal solution was successively washed with water, sodium bicarbonate solution, and water. After drying, the solvent was evaporated to furnish a solid ketone (1.5 g.), m.p. 80-120°, which afforded two isomeric 2,4-DNP derivatives, m.p. 257-58° and 230°, reported above.

The use of ten moles of potassium *t*-butoxide per mole of the ester (IX: R=Me) in the above Dieckmann cyclisation did not alter the yield of the ketone. Incidentally, hydrolysis of the β -keto-ester for longer period (6 hr.) decreased the yield of the ketone from 70 to 50%.

The above ketonic material (500 mg.), m.p. 80-120°, was chromatographed on alumina (15 g.) and eluted with petroleum (b.p. 60-80°), collecting 25 ml each time. The first four fractions were oils from which no homogeneous material could be obtained. Fractions (5-14) yielded a solid, m.p. 110-17°, which on repeated recrystallisation from methanol afforded a pure ketone, m.p. 142°, identical with that obtained from the above pyrolysis experiment.

(c). The Dieckmann cyclisation of the ester (IX: R = Me; 2 g.) with sodium hydride (220 mg.) and a drop of methanol under benzene (7 hr. reflux) provided an oily material

(no FeCl_3 coloration), which on hydrolysis afforded only the saturated dicarboxylic acid (IX: $\text{R} = \text{H}$; 1.8 g), m.p. 222° .

Equilibration of the Ketone, m.p. 142° —To sodium methoxide, prepared from sodium (320 mg.) and dry methanol (5 ml), was added the ketone (60 mg., m.p. 142°). The resulting mixture after refluxing under nitrogen for 2 hr. was poured over ice and extracted with ether. After drying, the solvent on evaporation provided an oil (55 mg.) which soon solidified, m.p. $80-120^\circ$. This material on once crystallisation from methanol yielded some crystals, which furnished a 2,4 DNP, m.p. $245-46^\circ$; recrystallisation from chloroform-ethyl-acetate furnished the pure material, m.p. $256-57^\circ$. The mother liquor after crystallisation of the ketone, m.p. $80-120^\circ$, afforded a DNP, m.p. $224-30^\circ$, which on recrystallisation as above yielded a pure DNP, m.p. 230° .

7-Ethyl-8-methyl-1,2-benzofluorene (I).—To the stirred Grignard complex, prepared from magnesium metal (440 mg.) and ethyl iodide (2.4 ml) in dry ether (50 ml), was added slowly a solution of the ketone (X, 1.5 g.), m.p. $80-120^\circ$, in dry ether (125 ml). The reaction mixture was kept cooled during the addition. After stirring for 6 hr., the mixture was left at the room temperature for 16 hr. This was then refluxed for 1 hr., decomposed with ice-cold ammonium chloride solution, the organic layer separated, and the aqueous layer was extracted with ether. The combined solvent was washed with water, dried, and evaporated to provide a yellow oil (1.9 g.). This material was dissolved in dry benzene (75 ml), *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (100 mg.) added, and the benzene was slowly distilled during 1 hr. The residue was taken up in ether and the solvent after usual processing was evaporated. The oily residue was subjected to a short-path distillation at $135-45^\circ/0.1$ mm to furnish olefinic compound (1.4 g.), which responded to tetranitromethane test. A middle cut was analysed. (Found: C, 90.82; H, 8.88. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{22}$ requires C, 91.55; H, 8.45).

The above unsaturated compound (1.37 g.) was dehydrogenated with 30% Pd-Cat 220- 310° under nitrogen atmosphere. The product was repeatedly extracted with ether and on removal of the solvent, a yellow solid (750 mg.) m.p. $130-35^\circ$, was obtained. This material on recrystallisation from acetone-methanol furnished crystalline plates (700 mg.), m.p. $147-50^\circ$, which were further purified by chromatography on alumina (40 g.). Light petroleum ($60-80^\circ$) eluates afforded plates (620 mg.), which on recrystallisation from acetone-methanol provided analytically pure 7-ethyl-8-methyl-1,2-benzofluorene, m.p. $151-52^\circ$. (Found: C, 92.72; H, 7.20. Calc. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{18}$: C, 92.98; H, 7.02%). $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{cyclohexane}}$ 222, 241, 249, 258, 268, 305, 317, and 333 μ ($\log \epsilon$, 4.58, 4.29; 4.46, 4.85, 5.08, 4.31, 4.30, and 3.47 respectively). The 2,4,7-trinitrofluorenone complex crystallised from benzene-ethanol as deep red crystals, m.p. $195-96^\circ$. (Found: C, 68.92; H, 4.51; N, 7.21. $\text{C}_{33}\text{H}_{23}\text{O}_7\text{N}_3$ requires C, 69.10; H, 4.04; N, 7.32%). The mixed m.p. of the above hydrocarbon with an authentic sample¹⁵ (m.p. $150-51^\circ$) of Jacobs hydrocarbon remained undepressed.

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